

Development of Land Use Map of Eda Forest Reserve in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Land use of Eda forest reserve was delineated with a view to determining the various sections that constitute the forest ecosystem. Satellite imageries and sketch map of Eda Forest Reserve were obtained from google earth and Ekiti State Department of Forestry respectively to produce a base map. Coordinates of some places within the forest reserve that could easily be identified both on the map and directly on the ground were also obtained using hand held global positioning system (GPS) receiver (Garmin GPS 76). Photographs of the forest reserve were taken for the purpose of hotlinking. The coordinates, satellite imageries, sketch maps and photographs obtained were loaded into Quantum GIS for analysis. The satellite imageries and sketch map were georeferenced using the coordinates obtained from the forest reserve. Map of the forest reserve was generated showing the various land use (natural forest, Terminalia superba, Gmelina arborea and Tectona grandis plantations) within the forest ecosystem, which involves vectorization of the raster data model, map production and image processing. Various forest types were represented with polygons of different colours and sizes, road was represented with line. The photographs obtained were used to hotlink various sections of the forest to the digital map produced. It was observed that the natural forest in Eda Forest Reserve occupied the larger portion of the reserve and it accounted for 57.7% of the total land cover while plantations of Gmelina arborea, Tectona grandis and Terminalia superba accounted for 15.5% of the total land cover of the forest reserve. The remaining 26.8% of the forest reserve has been lost to degradation.

Keywords: Eda Forest Reserve, Land use, Plantation, Natural Forest and Global Positioning System.

INTRODUCTION

Land use change has direct effects on the world's ecosystems through habitat destruction and alteration of competitive relationships but also indirect effects through alteration of fire frequency and nutrient and water balances (Mooney and Hofgaard, 1999). Land use change is a major contributor to the introduction and spread of alien invasive species which, in turn, are the second most important threat to biodiversity, behind habitat destruction (FAO, 2005). Land use changes can promote the emergence or re-emergence of infectious diseases which degrade human health and that of other species (Morse, 1995; Vitousek *et al.*, 1997). Infectious disease agents often, and perhaps typically, are alien invasive species since they are invaders over most of their range (McNeely *et al.*, 2001). Forest activities, such as clear-cutting and road building, may increase exposure of workers to infectious diseases such as human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), Ebola, hemorrhagic fever, Marburg hemorrhagic fever, yellow fever, leishmaniasis, malaria and Ross River virus disease (Morse, 1995; Daszak *et al.*, 2000; Chivian, 2002). Clear cutting of the forest ecosystem also results in deforestation, de-reservation and reduction in economic resources and biodiversity within the forest ecosystem. Deforestation is a serious problem in Nigeria, which currently has one of the highest rates of forest loss (3.3 %) in the world (FAO, 2005).

Since 1990, the country has lost some 6.1 million hectares or 35.7 percent of its forest cover. Worse, Nigeria's most biodiverse ecosystems—its old-growth forests—are disappearing at an even faster rate. Between 1990 and 2005, the country lost a staggering 79 % of these forests and since 2000 Nigeria has been losing an

average of 11 percent of its primary forests per year—doubles the rate of the 1990s. These figures give Nigeria the dubious distinction of having the highest deforestation rate of natural forest on the planet (FAO, 2005). Consequently, it is important to know the series of operation carried out on our forest estates by examining and mapping the various land use in our forest reserves. This will help forest managers to forestall further deforestation and consequent dereservation and desertification. A case study of Eda forest reserve in Ekiti State, Nigeria is examined in this study.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Eda forest reserve in Ekiti State, Nigeria. It is located between Latitudes 7° 23'N and 7° 46'N and Longitudes 4° 47' and 5° 45'E. The State covers a total land area of 6,353 km². (Alo *et al.*, 2012; Alo, 2013; Alo *et al.*, 2014). Satellite images of the forest reserve were obtained from the Google Earth while the sketch map of the forest reserve was obtained from Ekiti State Department of Forestry (ESDF). Coordinates of some places that could easily be identified on satellite images and directly on land - such as T-junctions, settlements, major roads, major rivers and major hills within the forest reserve - were obtained using handheld Global Positioning System (GPS). These were used in georeferencing the sketch map. Coordinates of the boundaries of various forest types within the forest reserve were obtained. Photographs of the forest reserve showing both the natural and artificial forest as well as capturing all the tree species in the plantations within the reserve were obtained.

Satellite imagery and sketch maps were georeferenced. Colour enhancement was done in such a way to be able to digitize various sections and features of the forest reserve. This was followed by

categorization. At this stage, the satellite imagery was categorized into various sections using different colours. This was followed by vectorization, which involves the conversion of raster data to vector by digitization. This was followed by map production. The digitized boundaries were superimposed on the satellite images after which clipping was done. Different forest types within the forest reserve were digitized as polygons with distinct colours. Lines of different thickness and colours were used for roads while town, was represented with point.

RESULTS

The sketch map of Eda forest reserve, which was produced in the early 1950s and retraced in October, 1953 was not georeference and lack adequate details (Figure 1). However, the digital maps produced in this study provide adequate details on various forest types and land use (Figures 2 to 5). A comparison of the old sketch map of Eda Forest Reserve and the maps produced in this study revealed some significant changes within forest reserve over time. For instance, “Pakunde” in the sketch map is the old name of Isinbode-Ekiti town. This is buttressed by the fact that the only town at southern part of Eda II is Isinbode – Ekiti and was confirmed by the old dwellers of the town. The cocoa farm originally present at the south of Eda I in the sketch map no longer exist.

Figure 1: Sketch map of Eda Forest Reserve, Ekiti State, Nigeria (Source: Ekiti State Department of Forestry)

Eda I comprises mainly of plantation forests (Figure 2) while Eda II is mostly made up of natural forest (Figure 3). Eda I accounted for 42.27% of the entire land cover of the reserve (Table 1), which is made up of three major plantation species: *Gmelina arborea*, *Tectona grandis* and *Terminalia superba*.

Figure 2: Land cover map of Eda I part of Eda Forest Reserve, Ekiti State, Nigeria

Figure 3: Land cover map of Eda II part of Eda Forest Reserve

Natural vegetation is situated at the southern part and accounts for the largest part of the reserve, followed by plantations of both *Gmelina arborea* and *Tectona grandis*, which accounts for 21.51% and 9.05% of the total land area of Eda I and the entire Eda Forest Reserve respectively (Table 1) and situated at the northern part of the reserve. *Terminalia spp* plantation is the smallest of all the plantations in Eda I and accounted for 15.18% and 6.40% of the total land area of Eda I and the entire Eda Forest Reserve respectively (Table 1). It has little quantity of *Terminalia ivorensis* at the fringe and is situated at the southwestern part of the reserve.

Table 1: Sizes of various land use in Eda Forest Reserve

	Land use	Size km ²	% Size of Eda I	% Size of the Forest Reserve
Eda I	Natural forest	0.35	9.11	3.86
	<i>Terminalia spp</i>	0.58	15.18	6.40
	<i>Gmelina</i> and <i>Teak</i> Plantations	0.82	21.51	9.05
	Rock Outcrop	0.12	3.04	1.32
	High Dense Forest	0.02	0.61	0.22
	Harvested <i>Gmelina</i> and <i>Teak</i> Plantations	0.17	4.51	1.88
	Natural vegetation	1.64	42.76	18.10
	Degraded <i>Terminalia spp</i>	0.13	3.30	1.43
Eda I Total		3.83	100.00	42.27
Eda II	Natural Forest	5.23	-	57.73
	Gross Total	9.06	-	100.00

Information obtained from the old dwellers of the town, and Forest Guards revealed that at the early stage of the plantation establishment, there was incidence of fire outbreak in *Terminalia*

spp plantation, which destroyed part of the seedlings and were never replaced. This fire outbreak was responsible for the degraded portion and brought about reduction in the survival rate. A portion of the remaining plantation was observed to have been encroached upon by illegal fellers, probably because the species is indigenous and economically valuable for timber purpose. This information was gathered from personal communication with some of the old villagers and the Forest Guards who accompanied us to the forest.

It was observed that within *Gmelina arborea* and *Tectona grandis* plantations, some portions have been harvested. This was evident in the coppices that sprouted out of the stumps usually between 3 and 7 trees (coppices) per stump. There were also evidences of encroachment by the farmers into the *Gmelina* plantations. Within *Gmelina* and teak plantations, stands of *Theobroma cacao* were evident. However, only a small portion of the *Terminalia species* plantations have been encroached upon towards the southern and northern parts of the reserve. Within the natural vegetation portion of the reserve, there are farm lands especially at the center. At the northeastern part of the reserve lie rock outcrops, one of which is Itake rock. There are two roads within the reserve, which are: Eda- Ilasa road and Eda- Ayebode road. The largest part of the reserve, which was occupied by natural vegetation, is a proof that areas devoid of plantations are either not planted or have been cropped over time and natural growth of plant species occurred. Degraded land within the plantations of *Gmelina arborea* and *Tectona grandis* is due to the fact that the trees were removed from the plantations severally over time without following a particular pattern of harvesting. Sequel to this incessant removal of tree species from plantation, farmers were able to have access into the plantations and its buffer for farming activities. It was observed that in Eda Forest Reserve, farmers have already started planting perennial crops such as *Theobroma cacao* at the southern part of the plantation of *Gmelina arborea* and

Tectona grandis. It is feared that if nothing is done to stop this trend, the farmers might take over the entire plantation. This level of de-reservation by farmers characterizes tropical zones where the largest portion of global net forest loss is recorded (Gibbs *et al.*, 2010). This is as a result of sustained and increasing demand for agricultural products for food and energy (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011; FAO, 2012).

Eda II is situated at the southern part of Eda I and demarcated by

Eda-Omuo Ekiti road (Figure 4). Eda II consists of natural forest and accounted for 57.73 % of the total land cover of Eda Forest Reserve (Figure 3). The natural forest portions of the reserve could be described as dense high forest, which is still relatively untouched in terms of exploitation. This is because the State Government has put restrictions on the forest reserve in the last six years for timber exploitation

Figure 4: Land cover map of Eda Forest Reserve

Hotlinks of some land-uses within Eda Forest Reserve are presented in Figure 5. The figure shows the picture of *Tectona grandis* plantation and natural vegetation at the top right and left corners respectively while the dense high forest and tree stands within the forest are presented at the bottom. The essence was to present a pictorial representation of exactly how the forest looks in

parts as was done by Agbelade and Akindele (2013) when they mapped out the tree species diversity of Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria and hotlinked some parts of the University with the map generated. The reduction in original land use over time has led to deforestation, which is at an alarming rate (Aina and Salau, 1992; Gutti *et al.*, 2012; Udoakpan, *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 5: Screen shots of hotlinks of some land-uses within Eda Forest Reserve, Ekiti State, Nigeria

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated the use of Geographical Information System (GIS) in land use and map production which can be used in all areas of human endeavour such as Forestry and Environment Management, monitoring of the space and earth structures, Natural resources development and Engineering Land as a natural resource provides an avenue for change in land use. The development of a new map for Eda forest reserve with relevant details unlike the old sketch map reveals that GIS can be used accurately to identify the different land use and vegetation type of an area. The research work has shown how GIS technology has capability to generate reliable information that can be used in mapping land use of a forest reserve.

RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that forest managers should take advantage of GIS technology to update the changes that occurs in the forest ecosystem within a relatively short time to accommodate various land uses as a result of the changes.

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